

Mapping physiognomies in Cerrado remnants with Satellite Image Time Series: a case study around the Batalha Hydroelectric Reservoir, Goiás (Brazil)

Izaias de S. Silva,¹ Diego T. F. Nascimento²

UFG, Goiânia, GO

Claudio A. de Almeida,³ Luciana S. Soler,⁴ Felipe C. de Souza⁵

INPE, São José dos Campos, SP

Marta P. da Luz⁶

PUC Goiás, Goiânia, GO | Eletrobras, Rio de Janeiro, RJ

Resumo

Cerrado remnants are a crucial component in maintaining a diversity of ecosystem services at the landscape scale. Satellite images have been the main data set used to map land use and land cover in the Brazilian Cerrado. However, the detailed mapping of Cerrado physiognomies using satellite images is still a significant challenge. The literature describes the challenges in accurately distinguishing vegetation classes due to their significant spatial and seasonal variability in photosynthetic activity, along with their high spectral similarity. This case study aimed to map the physiognomies on the highest hierarchical level (Level I) of natural vegetation formations in a contributing watershed of the Batalha Hydroelectric Power Plant reservoir, located in eastern Goiás, a core region of Cerrado. We used the attribute Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) of the Sentinel-2/MSI Satellite Image Time Series (SITS) provided by the Brazil Data Cube (BDC) for the hydrological year (2021 - 2022). The Random Forest algorithm and the best practices for assessing the accuracy of the mapping were adopted. The results show the mapping of physiognomies with an overall accuracy of 0.80. Among Savanna and Grassland, where the transition is gradual and there is structural and density variation in vegetation, most classification errors were observed.

1 Introduction

The Brazilian Cerrado, the most biodiverse Neotropical Savanna of the world, is a global conservation hotspot due to its high concentration of endemic flora and fauna species [11]. As the second largest biogeographic system in South America [1], Cerrado plays a critical role in maintaining essential ecosystem services, including carbon balance regulation and water production [12], contributing directly to eight of Brazil's twelve main hydrographic regions. Currently, the Brazilian Cerrado holds the fastest growing agricultural frontier in Brazil [7]. The expansion of these activities has not only significantly removed natural vegetation cover (deforestation) [2], but has also led to the intense fragmentation of its once continuous landscapes, one of the leading causes of species extinction and decline [6].

According to official data [8], it is estimated that over 50% of the natural vegetation cover of the Brazilian Cerrado has already been lost, with deforestation increasing at a rate of 25% in 2022 compared to

¹izaias@discente.ufg.br

²diego_nascimento@ufg.br

³claudio.almeida@inpe.br

⁴luciana.soler@inpe.br

⁵felipe.carvalho@inpe.br

⁶martaluz@eletrobras.com

2021. Official data also indicate that Goiás state currently ranks third among Brazilian Federal Units with the highest annual increase in the suppression of natural vegetation cover in the Brazilian Cerrado [8]. The literature shows that orbital remote sensing data have been the primary data set used to measure changes in Land Use and Land Cover (LULC), as well as to identify and map vegetation types in the Brazilian Cerrado [13, 15, 23]. Traditionally, semi-automatic and automatic classification techniques have been applied, the latter based on Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) methods [3, 5, 14]. However, the detailed mapping of Cerrado physiognomies using satellite images is still a significant challenge [14].

The inherent difficulty in distinguishing the physiognomies of the Cerrado using satellite images is due to its high diversity of vegetation formations, spatial and seasonal variability in photosynthetic activity, as well as their pronounced spectral similarity [9, 14, 20]. This combination of factors demands not only the adoption of high spatial resolution images, but also the performance analysis of different methods to discriminate subtle nuances in the data [5, 18]. In this context, the analysis of SITS emerges as a relevant approach for large-scale environmental monitoring and mapping [24, 26]. SITS can capture significant changes in LULC, as well as enable a more comprehensive and contextualized understanding of the continuous vegetation ecological dynamics, essential for the precise mapping of vegetation [17, 24, 26].

To support time series analysis, collections of satellite images have been organized as multidimensional data cubes [4]. Retrieved SITS from data cubes can be integrated with ML and DL algorithms, potentially leading to significant advancements in LULC mapping compared to traditional methods [28]. In this context, this study aimed to use the technologies available under the BDC project, operated by the National Institute for Space Research (INPE), to map the physiognomies of vegetation in Cerrado remnants. Specifically, we sought to classify Cerrado physiognomies at the highest hierarchical level (Level I), as proposed by Ribeiro and Walter [21]. The study area encompassed a contributing watershed of the Batalha Hydroelectric Power Plant reservoir, located in eastern Goiás, a core region of the Brazilian Cerrado.

Although fragmented, Cerrado remnants are a key component in maintaining and regulating a diversity of ecosystem services in the Direct Contribution Basins of Water Reservoirs [25]. It includes those related to the hydrological cycle, such as water infiltration, aquifer recharge, erosion prevention, and sediment retention, as well as services associated with soil nutrient cycling [19]. Accurate mapping of physiognomies in Cerrado remnants provides essential information for native vegetation protection and restoration policies, such as the Cerrado Vegetation Conservation Plan. Therefore, it is crucial to identify and map them to understand their structure and assess their integrity at a landscape scale, thus providing information that can support decision-making [27].

2 Methodology

This study employed SITS of the Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI) [10], derived from Sentinel-2 Multispectral Instrument (MSI) data. Specifically, the analysis was conducted using Analysis-Ready Data (ARD) from the BDC project, georeferenced and clipped to the BDC-Small V2 grid with a 16-day temporal composition (SENTINEL-2-16D). The dataset employs the Least Cloud Cover First (LCF) best-pixel approach.

The study focused on the regional hydrological year (October 2021 – September 2022), ensuring alignment with the region's annual hydrological cycle. The initial training dataset comprised 1,195 samples labeled according to Level I Cerrado physiognomies (Forest Formations, Savanna Formations, and Grass Formations), as defined by [21]. The samples were generated through fieldwork conducted in January 2025 and visual interpretation of Sentinel-2 MSI images. We used the "Primary Natural Vegetation" class from the TerraClass Project (2022) as a spatial mask to ensure consistency with Cerrado remnants while aligning with Brazil's official land cover classification data.

SITS were extracted from the data cube using the `sits` package [26], an open-source R package. Pre-processing techniques were applied to sample analysis and quality control, following the method proposed by [22], which employs Self-Organizing Maps and Bayesian inference. Using the k-fold validation method, we performed cross-validation ($K = 5$) and evaluated the generalization and robustness of different Random

Forest models. Subsequent steps included training of the model; generating the respective probability maps of physiognomies; applying Bayesian smoothing for map refinement; reclassifying with label assignment; and finally, assessing accuracy according to the method proposed by [16], using a total of 379 samples.

3 Results and Discussion

The mapping of Cerrado physiognomies in the study area achieved an overall accuracy of 0.80. User's Accuracies (UA) for Forest, Savanna, and Grass Formations were 0.96, 0.98, and 0.48, respectively, while Producer's Accuracies (PA) were 0.81, 0.72, and 0.95. The F1-score for Forest, Savanna, and Grass Formations were 0.87, 0.84, and 0.63, respectively. Despite an overall accuracy of 0.80, the map has limitations, with an significant confusions between Savanna and Grass Formations. We observed a commission bias (false positives) for the Grass Formation class, and omission bias (false negatives) for the Savanna Formation class. In view of this aspects, the results shows current training samples don't capture adequately the distinguishing characteristics between these classes.

Figure 1. Cerrado physiognomies map.

The difficulty in distinguishing Savanna from Grassland Formations is non-trivial. This is a well-documented limitation in the literature [5, 14, 20]. The construction of a high-quality training dataset is another inherent challenge in vegetation mapping. The classification uncertainties were observed predominantly in transitions areas of the Savanna and Grass Formations, where the structural gradients and the vegetation density present subtle differences [21]. Distinguishing between vegetation physiognomies in this transitional landscapes remains a challenge. We recommend that future studies incorporate additional attributes into EVI, including contextual data such as soil, elevation, slope, as well as radar data. Furthermore, we suggest evaluating other ML classifiers, including also DL approaches.

The BDC and the `sits` package enable consistent large-area LULC mapping [26]. Considering that satellite image time series provide a more comprehensive and contextualized understanding of vegetation dynamics, we emphasize that these technologies offer a robust approach for mapping the remaining native vegetation of the Brazilian Cerrado. Accurate maps of Cerrado remnant vegetation provide essential information for protecting remaining native vegetation, guiding vegetation restoration public policies, and planning watershed revitalization projects by the productive sector, especially in the landscapes surrounding water reservoirs [19].

Referências

- [1] A. N. Ab'Saber. **Os domínios de Natureza do Brasil: Potencialidades paisagísticas**. 3a. ed. São Paulo: Ateliê Editorial, 2003. ISBN: 9786555800319.
- [2] M. E. D. Chaves, G. Mataveli, E. Zu Ermgassen, R. B. A. Aragão, M. Adami e I. D. Sanches. “Reverse the Cerrado’s neglect”. Em: **Nature Sustainability** 6 (2023), pp. 1028–1029. DOI: [/10.1038/s41893-023-01182-w](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-023-01182-w).
- [3] D. F. Cho, S. F. Schwaida, R. E. Cicerelli, T. Almeida, A. P. M. Ramos e E. E. Sano. “Desempenho do Algoritmo de Classificação de Imagens Random Forest para Mapeamento do Uso e Cobertura do Solo no Cerrado Brasileiro”. Em: **Anuário do Instituto de Geociências** 3 (2021), pp. 1–11. DOI: [10.11137/1982-3908_2021_44_37979](https://doi.org/10.11137/1982-3908_2021_44_37979).
- [4] K. R. Ferreira, G. R. Queiroz, L. Vinhas, R. F. B. Marujo, R. E. O. Simões, M. C. A. Picoli, G. Camara, R. Cartaxo, V. C. F. Gomes, L. A. Santos, A. H. Sánchez, J. S. Arcanjo, J. G. Fronza, C. A. Noronha, R. W. Costa, M. C. Zagila, F. Zioti, T. S. Korting, A. R. Soares, M. E. D. Chaves e L. M. G. Fonseca. “Earth Observation Data Cubes for Brazil: Requirements, Methodology and Products”. Em: **Remote Sensing** 24 (2020), pp. 1–19. DOI: [10.3390/rs12244033](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12244033).
- [5] C. D. Girolamo-Neto. “Identificação de fitofisionomias de Cerrado no Parque Nacional de Brasília utilizando Random Forest aplicado a imagens de alta e média resoluções espaciais”. Tese de doutorado. INPE/MCTI, 2018.
- [6] T. O. Grande, L. M. S. Aguiar e R. B. Machado. “Heating a biodiversity hotspot: connectivity is more important than remaining habitat”. Em: **Landscape Ecology** 35 (2020), pp. 639–657. DOI: [/10.1007/s10980-020-00968-z](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-020-00968-z).
- [7] E. Hershaw e S. Sauer. “Land and investment dynamics along Brazil’s ‘final’ frontier: The financialization of the Matopiba at a political crossroads”. Em: **Land Use Policy** 131 (2023), pp. 1–15. DOI: [10.1016/j.landusepol.2023.106675](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2023.106675).
- [8] INPE. **Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais (INPE)**. Online. Acessado em 27/06/2025, <https://terrabrasilis.dpi.inpe.br/app/dashboard/deforestation/biomes>.
- [9] E. Lenza e C. A. Klink. “Comportamento fenológico de espécies lenhosas em um cerrado sentido restrito de Brasília, DF”. Em: **Brazilian Journal of Botany** 4 (2006), pp. 627–638. DOI: [10.1590/S0100-84042006000400013](https://doi.org/10.1590/S0100-84042006000400013).
- [10] H. Q. Liu e A. Huete. “A feedback based modification of the NDVI to minimize canopy background and atmospheric noise”. Em: **IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing** 2 (1995), pp. 457–465. DOI: [10.1109/TGRS.1995.8746027](https://doi.org/10.1109/TGRS.1995.8746027).
- [11] N. Myers, A. Mittermeier, C. G. Mittermeier, G. A. B. Fonseca e J. Kent. “Biodiversity hotspots for conservation priorities”. Em: **Nature** 403 (2000), pp. 853–858. DOI: [10.1038/35002501](https://doi.org/10.1038/35002501).
- [12] D. T. F. Nascimento e R. J. A. F. Gonçalves. **Águas do Cerrado: gestão, usos e conflitos**. 1a. ed. Goiânia: Kelps, 2018. ISBN: 9788540023321.
- [13] D. T. F. Nascimento e G. T. Novais. **Sistemas paisagísticos do Cerrado**. 1a. ed. Anápolis: Editora UEG, 2024. ISBN: 9786588502853.
- [14] A. K. Neves, T. S. Körting, L. M. G. Fonseca, A. R. Soares, C. D. Girolamo-Neto e C. Heipke. “Hierarchical mapping of Brazilian Savanna (Cerrado) physiognomies based on deep learning”. Em: **Journal of Applied Remote Sensing** 4 (2001), pp. 1–23. DOI: [10.1117/1.JRS.15.044504](https://doi.org/10.1117/1.JRS.15.044504).
- [15] M. T. Oliveira, H. L. G. Cassol, K. A. Ganem, A. C. Dutra, J. D. Prieto, E. Arai e Y. E. Shimabukuro. “Mapeamento da Vegetação do Cerrado – Uma Revisão das Iniciativas de Sensoriamento Remoto”. Em: **Revista Brasileira de Cartografia** 72 (2020), pp. 1250–1274. DOI: [10.14393/rbcv72nespecial50anos-56591](https://doi.org/10.14393/rbcv72nespecial50anos-56591).

- [16] P. Olofsson, G. M. Foody, M. Herold, S. V. Stehman, C. E. Woodcock e M. A. Wulder. “Good practices for estimating area and assessing accuracy of land change”. Em: **Remote Sensing of Environment** 2 (2014), pp. 42–57. DOI: [10.1016/j.rse.2014.02.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2014.02.015).
- [17] V. J. Pasquarella, C. E. Holden, L. Kaufman e C. E. Woodcock. “From Imagery to Ecology: Leveraging Time Series of All Available LANDSAT Observations to Map and Monitor Ecosystem State and Dynamics”. Em: **Remote Sensing in Ecology and Conservation** 2 (2021), pp. 152–170. DOI: [10.1002/rse2.24](https://doi.org/10.1002/rse2.24).
- [18] F. F. Ribeiro, D. A. Roberts, L. L. Hess, F. W. Davis, K. K. Caylor e G. A. Daldegan. “Geographic Object-Based Image Analysis Framework for Mapping Vegetation Physiognomic Types at Fine Scales in Neotropical Savannas”. Em: **Remote Sensing** 11 (2020), pp. 1–24. DOI: [10.3390/rs12111721](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12111721).
- [19] M. M. Sales, M. P. Da Luz, M. M. A. Mascarenha, J. C. Carvalho e V. D. Silva. **Erosão Hídrica e Dinâmica dos Sedimentos em Reservatórios**. 1a. ed. Goiânia: Escola de Engenharia Civil e Ambiental, 2024. ISBN: 9786554472456.
- [20] E. E. Sano, R. Rosa, J. L. S. S. Brito e L. G. Ferreira. “Land cover mapping of the tropical savanna region in Brazil”. Em: **Environmental Monitoring and Assessment** 1 (2010), pp. 113–124. DOI: [10.1007/s10661-009-0988-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-009-0988-4).
- [21] S. M. Sano, S. P. De Almeida e J. F. Ribeiro. **Cerrado: Ecologia e Flora**. 1a. ed. Brasília: Embrapa Cerrados, 2008. ISBN: 9788573833973.
- [22] L. A. Santos, K. R. Ferreira, G. Camara, M. C. A. Picoli e R. E. Simoes. “Quality control and class noise reduction of satellite image time series”. Em: **ISPRS Journal of Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing** 1 (2021), pp. 75–88. DOI: [10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2021.04.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.isprsjprs.2021.04.014).
- [23] C. A. M. Scaramuzza, E. E. Sano, M. Adami, E. L. Bolfe, A. C. Coutinho, J. C. D. M. Esquerdo, Maurano. L. E. P., I. S. Narvaes, F. J. B. Oliveira Filho, R. Rosa, E. B. Silva, D. M. Valeriano, D. C. Victoria, A. P. Bayma, G. H. Oliveira e G. B. Silva. “Land-Use and Land-Cover mapping of the Brazilian Cerrado based mainly on Landsat-8 satellite images”. Em: **Revista Brasileira de Cartografia** 72 (2017), pp. 1041–1051. DOI: [10.14393/rbcv69n6-44309](https://doi.org/10.14393/rbcv69n6-44309).
- [24] M. Schwieder, P. J. P. Leitão, M. M. C. Bustamante, L. G. Ferreira, A. Rabe e P. Hostert. “Mapping Brazilian savanna vegetation gradients with Landsat time series”. Em: **International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation** 52 (2016), pp. 361–370. DOI: [10.1016/j.jag.2016.06.019](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2016.06.019).
- [25] I. S. Silva, D. T. F. Nascimento, P. A. Romão, G. F. N. Silva, M. M. Sales e M. M. Da Luz. “Proposition of LULC mapping in progressive detailing for the surroundings of hydroelectric powerplant reservoirs: Case study for the Batalha (Brazil)”. Em: **International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation** 1 (2023), pp. 1–10. DOI: [10.1016/j.jag.2023.103218](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jag.2023.103218).
- [26] R. Simões, G. Camara, G. Queiroz, F. C. Souza, P. R. Andrade, L. Santos, A. Carvalho e K. Ferreira. “Satellite Image Time Series Analysis for Big Earth Observation Data”. Em: **Remote Sensing** 13 (2021), pp. 1–20. DOI: [10.3390/rs13132428](https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13132428).
- [27] D. P. Tubelis, A. Cowling e C. Donnelly. “Landscape supplementation in adjacent savannas and its implications for the design of corridors for forest birds in the central Cerrado, Brazil”. Em: **Biological Conservation** 3 (2004), pp. 353–364. DOI: [10.1016/j.biocon.2003.09.014](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biocon.2003.09.014).
- [28] C.E. Woodcock, T.R. Loveland, M. Herold e M.E. Bauer. “Transitioning from Change Detection to Monitoring with Remote Sensing: A Paradigm Shift”. Em: **Remote Sensing of Environment** 238 (2020), pp. 1–20. DOI: [10.1016/j.rse.2019.111558](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111558).